

Society For Heritage, Archaeology & Management

(Connecting the Heritage & Culture across the Globe)

e-Newsletter

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Editorial

Our “**Society for Heritage, Archaeology and Management**” has started its journey from 2nd October, 2020. During this time, pandemic was in full swing. Covid situation still persists even today but in spite of this hard time our Society has carved out a niche for itself in the domain of Heritage, Archaeology and Management. We bow to those scholars whose direct academic contributions and inspirations have been continuously enriching the Society through the last six months. We acknowledge the great enthusiasms shown by our board members and well wishers.

Even in this unprecedented phase of our life, some of our members have been engaged in pursuing the legal and official matters related to the Society's registration, Website development, E. library, E. journal. With the immense help of some of our EC members we have set up the Archives for the benefit of the Researchers who have keen interest to know about the varied aspects of Indian Culture.

On February 7th, 2020 SHAM successfully conducted a heritage tour – **“Heritage Walk & Cultural Reminiscence,”** in Hooghly District. Thirteen members participated and visited temple sites of Guptipara and other heritage sites in adjoining regions. The main purpose was to explore some lesser known heritage sites for understanding Bengal's cultural significance.

Society also celebrated the **World Heritage Day** by organizing a Symposium-**“Remembering the National and Local Heritages on Heritage Day”**. Our Board members, research scholars and students from different disciplines participated and exchanged their views.

With this sweeping view of sixth monthly activities of SHAM, we have finally decided to organize a webinar in collaboration with Draupadi Dream Trust, Delhi, in next quarter. The Topic would be- **“Cultural Heritage of Bengal- Past Present and Future”**

“My best wishes to everybody and take care”

-President

Dr. Durga Basu

President of Society For Heritage Archaeology & Management (SHAM)

Former Professor & HOD of Department of Archaeology, Calcutta University

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Events Organised By SHAM During This Quarter

Asmita Basu

1. Celebration of World Heritage Day

The World Heritage Day, also known as International Day for Monuments and Sites is celebrated on 18th April every year since 1983. The history behind the nomenclature of this day lies in the proposal given by the International Council on Monuments and Sites (ICOMOS) on 18 April 1982 to commemorate this day as The International Day for Monuments and Sites which was approved by the General Assembly of UNESCO in 1983. The main aim behind this is to promote awareness about the diversity of cultural heritage of humanity, their vulnerability and the efforts required for their protection and conservation.

To mark this occasion, SHAM organised an online symposium on the theme **“Remembering the National & Local Heritages on Heritage Day”** on 18th April 2021. The symposium was coordinated by the President of the society, Prof. (Dr.) Durga Basu. A number of executive members of the society actively participated in the symposium and raised pertinent issues related to Heritage conservation, preservation and management. There were various teachers, assistant professors, research scholars who not only participated in the discussion but also put forward their valuable suggestions. The different suggestions and proposals for adoption in the objectives and agenda of SHAM, given by the participants during the symposium have been compiled by our esteemed executive member Mr. Balaknath Bhattacharya, which are listed below.

1. Dr Biswajit Ray proposed to study the geo-archaeology of different archaeological sites including paleo channels in the vicinity to have a proper insight about the site and its cultural developments through ages. All the members agreed to the proposal and entrusted Dr Ray to devise and conduct short term courses of geo archaeology for the members as well as other scholars and researchers.

2. Dr Banani Bhattacharyya proposed to increase awareness about conservation of heritage by involving school and college students. She opined that school/college students should be made aware about their local heritages. She cited examples of the state of Haryana where she started this type of awareness programmes involving institutions and different govt organisations. She also stated that there is a course curriculum regarding conservation of heritage developed by different educational boards. We can exploit this provision through consultation with different heads of institutions to incorporate the course in the curriculum. Considering the pandemic situation, it has been proposed to conduct awareness programme through webinar. Dr Biswajit Ray took the responsibility to organise the webinar by contacting with different colleges of the district of Nadia.

3. Dr Durga Basu proposed to collect information about different tangible, intangible and material heritages in the localities of each member. Those should be photographed and documented. She has also proposed to develop a small museum to preserve the collected items

4. Dr Sharmistha De Basu spoke regarding the documentation of local heritage specifically the old houses of the locality having a distinct architectural style of yester years. These are apart from the palaces and Zamindar Houses but constructed by well to do middle class persons of early twentieth century or before. Considering the fact of rapid demolition of such houses these days, it is necessary to document it as early as possible.

5. Mr. Balaknath Bhattacharyya proposed to undertake heritage tour at least once in two months to the sites which require urgent intervention. Local students and enthusiasts may be motivated to undertake the preliminary conservation activities like cleaning and de-weeding. Proper documentation regarding the site including present condition and intervention required should be recorded.

Thus, the symposium has shed light on very significant aspects of local and national heritages. The crucial points observed from the symposium will definitely be incorporated into the future agendas of SHAM, so that the society has far-reaching effects on heritage awareness, studies and research.

Figure 1 Discussions during online Symposium

Figure 2 Discussions during online Symposium

2. Heritage Walk to the Historic District of Hooghly

Heritage tour is not simply an outing to a historic site or event. It is best described as tourism that creates and defines opportunities to experience the places, people, activities and artifacts that authentically represent our past and present. Through heritage tourism, we see, experience and feel our foundations, as we build towards the sustainable future. Heritage signifies many of the historical and cultural elements that make a city or region unique. To enhance our domain of knowledge we need to follow the course of Heritage cycle (Fig.1). The Heritage cycle demonstrates the effect of heritage by a series of actions such as by understanding the heritage—people will value it; by valuing heritage—people will want to care for it; by caring—people will enjoy its essence; from enjoying it—people will get a thirst to understand heritage.

Thus, to initiate the course of Heritage cycle, SHAM had organised a Heritage Walk to the historic district of Hooghly in West Bengal on 7th February 2021 with the objective of re-discovering our local heritage and glorious culture of Bengal. Some of the lesser-known heritage sites were chosen for this heritage trail which was immensely enriching and interesting for the all the heritage enthusiasts of our society.

Fig.1 Heritage Cycle

Places visited during the Heritage Walk:

➤ **Brindaban Chandra's Math (Guptipara)**

➤ **Ananda Bhairavi 25 Pinnacled Terracotta temple complex (Somra)**

➤ **Hanseswari Temple (Bansberia)**

➤ **Zafar Khan Ghazi Mosque and Dargah**

Asmita Basu Chatterjee
Treasurer, Society For Heritage
Archaeology

Terracotta plaques of Bhattabati Ratneshwar Temple, Murshidabad , West Bengal

Balaknath Bhattacharyya

Introduction

A five pinnacled Ratneswar Shiva Temple of triratha style along with peeda (pyramid) style spires is very famous for its terracotta plaques pasted on all four walls of the edifice is located in Bhattabati near Lalbagh , Murshidabad. Artistically the works are of superb quality which proves the dexterity of Bengal artisans of early eighteenth century. The subjects dealt with in the panels reveal a piece of social as well as religious history of the contemporary period.

History

The founder of the temple was Bangadhikari (revenue collector) Jaynarayan in early eighteenth century during the reign of Nawab Murshid Kuli Khan (1704-25 AD). According to a local anecdote 1200 (twelve hundred) Bhatt Brahmins from Karnataka settled here during the reign of Sultan Hossain Shah (1494-1519 CE) for which the place was named as Bhattabati. Presently there is no Bhatta Brahmin here.

Terracotta Panels

The temple is very famous for its terracotta panels. Four sides of the temple are decorated with terracotta panels. The panels may be listed and classified as follows:

Ramayana Plaques

Hanuman bowing down to the feet of Rama, slaying of golden deer (Marich) by Lord Rama, slaying of demoness Taraka, Rama, Laksmana and Sita strolling in the forest, haradhanu bhanga (breaking of bow of Lord Shiva) and Hanuman in front of Rama and Sita etc.

Krishna Leela Plaques

Extraction of butter by Jasoda and Lord Krishna , slaying of dhenukasur in a palm forest, Slaying Keshi the horse demon , famous Raas Mandala panel – where Shri Krishna and Radha are dancing along with their female companions circumambulating them.

Dasavatar plaques of Vishnu

Plaques of Matsya Avatar, Baman Avatar and Balaram Avatar are visible.

Devi Durga Panel

Plaques of Devi Durga as Mahishasurmardini along with Her entire family are there.

Chaitanya Leela

A very beautiful Terracotta art work of Sadavuja (having six hands) Gauranga (a very popular motif throughout Bengal) largest in West Bengal. The other one is Nityananda, Gauranga and Radha Krishna in same panel.

Yalis

One Yali figure having body of a horse and head of a lion is found. Other semi gods and goddess Kirtimukh, a fierce face of a demon is placed almost in every temple of Bengal to protect it from all evils. Gandharva the musicians of Swargalok having their lower portion as that of birds are found.

Social

In the social plaques there are rows of Mughal warriors. We may get ideas about the dresses weapons, head dresses, foot wears of Mughal soldiers of eighteenth century.

Assimilation of Shaiva, Shakta and Vaishnava religious ideals as depicted in the temple

Though there are various streams of antagonistic Hindu religious philosophies upto 16th century Bengal from seventeenth centuries due to advent of Baktibad of Lord Chaitanya also for other socio political factors assimilation of different Hindu religious streams are observed. Thus we have various Shaiva and Shakta panels in Vaishnava temples along with Krishna Leela and Chaitanya leela Panels and similarly in Shakta and Shaiva temples the panels of Krishna leela and Chaitanya are in plenty. In this Shiva temple also we have Krishna leela, Chaitanya panels along with Mahishasuramardini panels

Conclusion

Bhattabati Ratneswar temple apart from being a Hindu temple of repute not only reveals the contemporary socio religious culture but also pattern of Mughal revenue administration where Hindus were also appointed as top officials. It also gives idea about the dresses and ornaments sported by Bengali aristocrats and common people both male and female.

Figure 1 Bhattabati Ratneswar Temple

Figure 2 Mahishasuramardini with family

Figure 3 Sadavuja Gauranga

Balaknath Bhattacharyya

Ex-Dy General Manger (Finance), Damodar Valley Corporation- a PSU

Kunal- A Pre-Harappan Site in Haryana

Dr. Banani Bhattacharyya

Kunal (29°30'N 75°41'E), one of the earliest pre-Harappan sites in Haryana, located in the Ratia Tehsil of Fatehabad district in Haryana lies in the flood plain of now dried riverbed of mythical Saraswati. At present Department of Archaeology & Museums is excavating Kunal, Dist. Fatehabad, Haryana. It is spread over an area of almost 15-20 acre. The deposition regarding habitation is almost 7m in which the remains of pre-Harappan and Mature Harappan phases have been excavated. The present scientific clearance was carried out for 24 days from 7th – 31st December 2020 at the site.

The purpose of the present excavation was two fold:

- A. To understand the layout and organization of the Kunal settlement.
- B. To determine the cultural sequence at the site.

Excavation has offered a great opportunity for the Early Harappan studies in Indian sub-continent and will provide new prospects in future research on formation and antecedent stages of Classical Harappans. Archaeological evidence shows the indigenous cultural traits of the early inhabitants with add mixture of material attributes of contemporary regional pre-Harappan cultures from 5th Millennium BCE prevailing in the area; before the emergence of Early Harappan civilization.

Excavation at Kunal has revealed the remains of three successive occupational periods of the pre/early and mature Harappan culture, followed by the Painted Grey Ware culture. These three successive structural phases from pit dwelling to that of square and rectangular mud brick houses came to light and were supposed to be the earliest remains of pre-Harappan culture in this region of Indus.

Archaeological evidence shows the indigenous culture prevailing in the area before the emergence of Harappan civilization. The earliest C14 date from the site is 5700 to 6000 BCE. A fire altar has been discovered during scientific clearance at Kunal in the month of December 2020 from Trench no YC1 Quadrant II. It could have served no other purpose than a ritualistic one. These altars suggest fire worship. There is no evidence to suggest the worship of the mother goddess at this site. Within the citadel complex, the western side contained eight stairs of mud bricks. Stairs were attached to these platforms. Remnants of round fire-pit have been found. It was perhaps intended for some specific (perhaps religious) purpose by the community. Recovered remnants of animals, suggest a possibility of animal-sacrifice been performed.

The excavation yielded mud brick structures associated with pre-Harappan and early Harappan cultural material such as pottery, beads, bangles, copper objects, terracotta figurine, sling balls, bone objects, shell objects, steatite beads and a rectangular tablet made on steatite in this season. The pottery includes Hakra ware (mud appliqué, incised ware, chocolate slipped ware), black and red ware, red ware, gray ware, black ware, red slipped ware, black slipped

ware, painted ware (Monochrome, Bichrome). The shapes include handi, pots, bowls, deep bowls, pot with handle, dish on stand, vessels, shallow dishes, storage-jars, lids, miniature pots etc.

Figure 1 Aerial view of the Site

Figure 2 Close-up of Community Fire Alter with mud brick stairs

Dr. Banani Bhattacharya
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A brief note on Geo-archaeological study at the site “Debalgarh”

Dr. Biswajit Roy

Introduction: Our present concern 'Debalgarh' archaeological site may easily be mentioned as one of the most remarkable achievement so far as the recent Geo-archaeological study in Bengal is concerned. The artifacts of the area date back to eras as early as 3rd- 4th century, a period much prior to the Pre-Gupta era and shows evidence in the continuity of subsequent Gupta, Pala, Sena and Sultanate dynasties.

The ruins of architectural structure also indicate that the site has been an immense potential centre of both administration and economics in the Pala-Sena era.

Spatial Location: 'Debalgarh ' or ' Debola' of 'Debagram gram panchayat' under Gangnapur police station and adjacent Anuliya site under Ranaghat police station, Nadia district are nearly 75 k.m away from Kolkata.

Figure 1 Satellite Image of Debalgarh

The central location or the fort area of Debalgarh extends in an almost square pattern. Residual of four ancient earthen watch towers stand at four directions, covering almost one square km area. The central area of Debalgarh is located beside the palaeo-channel of river ' Marali'. The citadel location is much close and roughly eight kilometres away from the confluence of 'Marali' with river ' Ichhamati '.

Methodology: To asses properly the geo- archaeological importance an extensive microlevel survey has been carried out through years. Primary survey has been carried out for both purposes- to study the nature geo- archaeological significance and recovered artifacts in general and to obtain the detailing of paleo-channel analysis in particular. Both the palaeo-channel of river Ganga at Anulia and Marali at Debagram have been analysed.

Different parameters like changes of slope, study of recovered organic substances from the dried up river bed, nature of sedimentation, study of soil texture from collected samples have been done. After receiving the data compilation and analysis has been conducted in post-field study. Location of palaeo-channels along the tributaries and distributaries, spots of archaeological findings has been plotted in maps to represent the spatial dimension.

Figure 2 Satellite images with palaeochannel at Debalgarh

Concluding Observations:

Recently, with the help of local villagers a registered organisation named “Debagram Debol Raja Purattwa O Lokosanskriti Sangha” has been formed (July, 2016) to protect and display the artefacts for academic purpose. But without extensive and proper archaeological excavation it is possible hardly to discover the site properly.

Recently a team of high officials from The Asiatic society and state archaeology dept. has visited the site. The monthly bulletin of The Asiatic society (July, 2018) has described Debalgarh as 'a new archaeo- tourist destination of Bengal'. It is our privilege enough to have with us the team of ‘Society for Heritage, Archaeology and Management’ from the very first day of the recent activities.

From the recovered Gupta era gold coins, Bengal type amphora, architectural residuals, icons and sculptures along with thousands of artifacts it is evident enough that the site played a crucial role so far as the trade and commerce and cultural heritage of ancient Bengal is concerned. Future excavation and further researches may discover a highly influential centre of administration and defense of Pala-Sena period and may add a new chapter in the regional history. Several high mounds especially within forest area strongly recommend a proper archaeological excavation in this site.

Dr. Biswajit Roy

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Metal Findings From The Neo-Chalcolithic Site Kuanr In Keonjhar District Of Odisha: An Archaeometallurgical Study

Dr. Debasis Kumar Mondal
Prof. Ranjana Ray

Kuanr is the first reported Chalco-Neolithic site of Keonjhar district in Northern Odisha (Ray 1993). The site was discovered by Ranjana Ray of Department of Anthropology, University of Calcutta in 1993. Later survey was carried out by Debasis Kumar Mondal from the same institution. The site is on a mound and named after the nearby village Kuanr (21° 30' N, 85°28'E). It is situated on the north west of the NH6 near the culvert no.378. The mound is about 600 m above the sea level. The site is naturally fortified with the presence of *Masani nalla* and *Ghumura nalla*, which are the tributaries of River Baitarani. Cultural remains were found from the runnels coming from upper silty clay deposition.

Stratigraphy of the site has been observed by natural cliff section and trial digging. The Pleistocene bed is identified by gravel and silt layer, which is superimposed by a thin layer of *ghutin* which demarcates the Holocene bed. The soil of the top most surface is yellowish brown in colour but the eroded lower portion is reddish in colour. This bed had yielded the cultural materials.

Several seasons' exploration and trial digging had yielded assemblage of artifacts, such as, stone tools, potsherds, terracotta pieces, burnt clay pellets and metal ornaments. Metal objects found from the site include bangles, rings, amulets, bells and pendants in a beaded necklace (Ray and Mondal 2013).

Analysis of the metal objects found from the site Kuanr is done by the Department of Metallurgical Engineering, Jadavpur University in the year 1993. Archaeo-metallurgical analysis of some of the bangles found from the site suggests that the ornaments are made up of very old type of brass, alloy of copper (55 %) and zinc (33 %) with 8.5% of tin (Sn). Analysis showed that presence of 2 to 3% of iron (Fe) and 1% of lead (Pb) may be due to simultaneous reduction of chalcopyrite (Cu, Fe sulphide) and Lead-Zinc (Pb-Zn) sulphide ore by charcoal (Ray *et. al.* 2000:364-365).

From Kuanr a large number of crucibles with slag adhered to it had been found at the site. Crucibles are thick in nature, grit tempered and porous made from the locally available clay. An almost complete crucible was found from the trench. This is an important craft indicator of *cire-perdue* casting. The crucible has a maximum length of 9 cm with 8.6 cm of maximum breadth. The thickness is ranging from 1.3 to 3.1 cm. A channel having 5.8 cm length and 0.5 cm diameter is seen. This is the runner, along which the wax in the mould is run, leaving a gap into which molten metal can flow. The inner portion is slightly concave. There are two air holes for removing of molten wax and metal smokes.

The *cire-perdue* or lost wax process was used for casting brass ornaments in the area. The technology could be reconstructed with the help of metal ornaments and crucibles. A comparison with the process of manufacture of brass objects by the present day metal smiths of the state of Odisha suggests that the Kuanr people employed the solid casting method to make brass ornaments.

The site perhaps preserves the earliest evidence of brass metallurgy in eastern India belong to Neo-Chalcolithic period i.e. 2nd millennium BCE. Perhaps the scarcity of tin in the area is one of the reasons of early development of brass metallurgy here. It is also worthy mentioned that tribal people living in different parts of eastern India prefers brass ornaments and the craft is being continued at present by Dhokra artisans.

Figure 1 Geographical location and a view of the Kuanr mound which yielded the evidences of Neo-Chalcolithic brass ornaments and stone tools

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Jadu Patas in collection of State Archaeological Museum: West Bengal

Dr. Sumita Guha

Among the surviving folk tradition down the present era is the Patachitras or Scroll Paintings. Patas /Jaranopatas or scroll paintings are used to entertain and educate the unsophisticated rural audiences. The painters or the practitioner of this narrative art is called Patua. The Patua is a kind of minstrel. He goes from village to village, with a bag containing several scrolls.

The patuas of West Bengal are extremely varied. Their audience is mainly Hindu or Muslims, sometimes Tribal people. The themes are inspired by the sacred texts of each of these religious communities.

Jadu patas- Jadupatas are tribal patas of the Santhal tribes of eastern India. It is a distinct tradition done by non-tribal chitrakar known as Jadupautas. They prepare these patas for the tribal community, associated with rituals, myths, legends beliefs associated with the life cycle of the tribal people.

Figure 1 Jadu Patas

JADU PATUA- Like the patuas, the Jadupatuas are painters and story tellers and go from village to village carrying their painted scrolls. These painters are called magic painters because they paint to preserve the crops, avert diseases, honoured the dead and so on. When somebody dies in the village “the artist magician” visits the family of the dead with a small and simple image (with some article which they hope to receive from the family of the dead person) which is supposed to represent the dead in a simple way according to age and sex. Only the late person’s pupil is missing. Showing this image to the family, the Jadu Patua tells the story evoking the suffering of the dead whose soul is still trapped in hell. For rendering back the eyesight they demand some articles shown in the picture. To help the deceased person the relatives needed to send some gift offering (daan) to the Jadu Patua , to intervene on their behalf. The Patua then performs the chakshudan or bestowal of eye sight. In the ritual, the Jadu Patu as magically endows the deceased’s well being in the after life through symbolic bestowal of eye-sight (chakshudan). By supplying the missing pupil in the portrait the Jadu Patua assures the relatives of the deceased that their loved ones will no longer have to wander blindly in the next world and thus freed his soul and send it to heaven. A chicken or a bowl or an umbrella at the bottom of the pata indicates what the patua expects as an offering. The Jadu Patuas also help the tribes in immersing the symbolic *asthi* of the dead in the holy water of a river which is sometimes far away from the house of the deceased and the family cannot afford to go there to perform the last right. They pay the Jadupatuas to go to the holy river and make a symbolic immersion of the bones by immersing the drawing/Patas in water.

Late Shri Gurusaday Datta during his tour to all parts of the then Bengal Presidency for collecting and rediscovering the folk culture of Bengal fetched this story.

Sumita Guha Sarkar

Assistant Curator, State Archaeological Museum, West Bengal

Veera Narayana Temple: A Heritage Jewel of the Chikmagalur District in Karnataka

Asmita Basu

The state of Karnataka emerged as a great centre of Hoysala temples. The Hoysala Kings who ruled over Mysore and the neighbouring regions from 1047 century to 1300 century A.D. had built several magnificent temples, dedicated to various Gods, specially to lord Shiva and Vishnu. These temples portrayed certain unique architectural patterns and were distinguished by their sublime stone craftsmanship.

The Veera Narayana temple is located in Belavadi, a village in the Chikmagalur district of Karnataka, India. The temple was built during the rule of the Hoysala Empire. The Veera Narayana Temple of Belavadi is supposed to be one of the best and the largest Hoysala monument surviving. The temple of Belavadi is located 29kms, south west of Chikmagalur District in south Karnataka . The temple was built during 1200 A.D. by the great Hoysala king Veera Ballala II. It is a Vaishnavite temple exemplifying a unique combination of artistic persuasion and architectural grandeur. The temple has a huge hut style Mukhamandapa which leads to the main shrine area (Fig. 1).

Like many other Hoysala temples, Veera Narayana temple is a Trikuta temple which includes three separate shrines with distinct and elegantly carved towers. The temple was built in two stages. Initially it was an ekakuta type temple with a closed hall. The galleries forming a cloister were attached originally with the ekakuta shrine. During the later phase two more shrines facing each other were connected to the main temple. The temple is built in star shaped architecture (Fig.2) which is a very unique style in itself. The garbha grihas of the temple enshrine the images of Veeranarayana, Venugopala and Yoga-Narasimha.

This temple can be considered as a heritage jewel in the Belavadi area. This small village is not much visited by tourists as the awareness about this heritage site, protected by ASI is less among the common visitors. Even though, this temple in Belavadi is located at a distance of only 12 kms from the UNESCO World Heritage Site of Halebidu, still it needs more promotion in order to attract tourists.

Figure 3: Mukhamandapa and entrance to Veeran Narayana Temple

Figure 4: Star shaped temple architecture

Asmita Basu Chatterjee
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Image inpainting: Bishnupur terracotta Temples

Mainak Biswas
Sanghita Kundu

For hundreds of years, Bishnupur, a municipal town in West Bengal's modern-day Bankura district was a center of culture, sculpture, and architecture. The town is also well-known for its terracotta temples, which are lavishly decorated with carved and molded terracotta decorations crafted from locally available local clay. These temples are linked to the Gaudiya Vaishnava religion. Due to the lack of maintenance, awareness, the conditions of those temples are going in a bad phase. The designs, the art, the historical storytelling terracottas have been destroyed day by day. Recently, few researchers used some process to repaint or repair the destroyed portion of the terracotta work, electronically. Here an image processing technique is discussed to repair the terracotta design. Figure 1 shows the original design of a temple of Bishnupur, whereas figure 2 shows the missing portion of that image and marked that in green color and finally figure 3 shows the repaired version using image inpainting.

Figure 1 Input image with missing terracotta

Figure 2: Missing portion of terracotta (--- marked in green color)

Figure 3 Inpainting version after restoration

The exemplar-based inpainting approach is used to fill complex regions in the input image. A mask is a logical representation that represents the target regions of an image that would be filled with inpainting. To restore the blurred image area, the original image needs to be repainted. Picture inpainting is the process of restoring a damaged or incomplete area of an image by copying appropriate visual material from the known portion of the image. This method was proposed for a variety of uses, including digital reproduction of old pictures, vintage records, and old paintings. The algorithms in these programs mostly deal with various forms of objects such as water blotches and cracks. Many image recognition and computer vision experts are now attempting to recreate damaged heritage artifacts in digital space. In this study a wide number of photographs of Bishnupur temples have been analyzed in order to incorporate image inpainting methods for restoring damages in heritage objects. The objective is to digitally repair the temples' damaged, incomplete, or destroyed terracotta pieces. The majority of the sample images have complex textures (macro) and configurations, making inpainting a difficult problem for these images.

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The Status of Women in our Society

Jenifar Begam

Women during the Vedic period occupied an exalted position and they enjoyed a fair amount of personal freedom and equal rights with men. They enjoyed independence and self-reliance. Besides their domestic role, they had every access to education with tremendous potential to realize the highest truths. They also played an important role in maintaining the economic status of the family with the occupation of spinning, weaving, and needlework. Widow's remarriage and inter caste marriage were also permitted in Rig Vedic society. Women learned several disciplines that included vocal and instrumental music and dance. Respect and value of the women in the Vedic society was in high terms not only as household mistress but also as individuals with great potential to contribute to human society. The Vedic period was termed as period of feminine glory and prestigious life. Works by ancient Indian grammarians such as Patanjali and Katyayana also suggest the high status of women in the early Vedic period.

But the scenario changed from the middle ages. The women were not too educated; they were early married, had to obey orders of their husband and elderly of the family and were kept in isolation when it came to major decision related to the family. Other than this Sati pratha, Child marriage, female infanticide, dowry system etc was privileged widely. In one sentence a woman was considered a man's possession.

Figure 1 Women writer of Ancient period

In the letter period, the practices of middle ages were abolished by notable personalities like Raja Ram Mohan Roy, Swami Vivekananda, Ishwar Chandra Vidyasagar, and others who worked hard for the wellbeing of women. Child Marriage Restraint Act was also passed by the constitution. Women's empowerment and gender equality was more emphasized. It includes increasing a woman's sense of self-worth, her decision-making power, her access to opportunities and resources, her power and control over her own life inside and outside the home, and her ability to effect change. Empowered women and girls contribute to the health and productivity of their families, communities, and countries, creating a ripple effect that benefits everyone.

But is it completely true or partial? Yes gender equity is emphasized right now, yes women are even more educated, they hold respected position in public and private sectors, then why does the same woman have to face physical assault, domestic violence, sexual assault, homicide etc. at home or work place. Thousands of women get raped everyday in our country, be a kid, teenager or adult. Is this because somewhere deep down there are men who feel themselves more dominating than women, or because women make them feel so? Questions which remain unanswered even in 21st century. Wish the Vedic culture regenerates someday again.

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Unique Bronze Vessel from Shang Dynasty of Ancient China

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It is traditionally believed that Chinese civilization appeared in the Yellow River Valley. However, recent archaeological evidence shows that the origins of Chinese civilization are much more complex. During the Neolithic period, a number of different cultures merged into day's mainland China. Each of the sepultures was different, but had common characteristics.

Around 1600 BC, the Shang founded the oldest Chinese dynasty. During the Shang Dynasty, many people lived in fortified settlements, which were significantly larger than that of the late Neolithic period. From about 1300 to 1050 BC, the Shanghai Royal Family ruled their people from the capital near Anyang City which was formerly located in Erligang. Both Anyang and Erligang were located in present-day Henan Province. The most important role of King Shang was that of a spiritual mediator for the royal clan, its subjects and the gods. In the Shang faith, the supreme deity of Di, or Shang Di, was a powerful force that ruled over the known universe. Shang Di also ruled over natural spirits and the spirits of royal ancestors. The king was responsible for performing the ceremonies to ensure the health and well-being of his family and subjects. This was often done by direct reference to the royal ancestors, who were believed to act as intermediaries between the king and Shang Di. Divination was also an important part of the king's role as a political and religious leader. A large number of tortoise-shells and ox-blades were used as oracle bones to record questions asked by the king about the spirits of the royal ancestors. The Shang kings asked about everything from the weather to the results of births, hunts and battles. Thus, the Shang kings played important political roles by engaging in state issues through religious rituals. The religious rites of the Shang Dynasty also reflect the importance of family relationships and lineages in Shang society. It is also important to note that in all of Chinese history, the Shang Dynasty, the male line has been considered the most important. So the kings conducted formal services of worship rather than female members of the royal family. Bronze played an important role in the religious and military life of Shang. Religious ceremonies, which included human and animal sacrifices, and sacrifices of wine and food in decorated bronze vessel. Bronze vessels were often buried with members of the royal family.

Wine containers were one of the most popular bronze objects of the Shang Dynasty. The number and variety of wine containers from Shang suggests that wine played an important role in Shang's religious rituals. The military relied on bronze technology for defensive purposes. The Shang military was equipped with bronze weapons and chariots that had bronze preparations. During the Shang Dynasty, jade was still highly valued. Bi and cong were again made predominantly for ritual functions in Shang. However, Shang also created many cores for personal decoration. Fig.1 demonstrates Bronze vessel from Shang Dynasty, 15th–14th Century B.C.E. measuring 21.9X14.5X16.0 cm. This unique wine vessel may have been used as a

container for heating wine prior to its consumption during religious rites performed in the Shang royal temple.

Fig.1: Ritual Wine Container (Jia) China

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Non-Renewable Energy To Renewable Energy: Identifying A Potential Energy Source In West Bengal

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Now a day it's very challenging to us for managing the energy for utilizing our daily needs of electricity. Our non-renewable energy resources are depleting at an alarming rate. Despite the fact that demands for electricity is steadily increasing. Most electricity come from consumption of coal energy and that can be reduced by using renewable energy. West Bengal, like the rest of India, needs to understand the immense potential of renewable energy and focus on developing the framework for production of renewable energy. Switching to renewable energy sources for generation of electricity will prove to be an efficient management strategy from not only the economic aspect, but also the environment point of view. This will definitely induce sustainable growth and development of the state.

This research focuses on West Bengal (WB), which has a lot of renewable resources. With 23 districts depicted in Figure 1, West Bengal is one of India's most important states in respect to renewable energy production. Different types of climates can be found in these 23 districts. Some regions will be ideal for solar energy, and others will be suitable for wind energy. There are also certain places that are suitable for both. So, when it comes to green energy options, West Bengal is the best place to look for.

Figure 5 Districts of West Bengal

According to the variation of Solar Intensity and Wind Intensity ,we can easily differentiate that 9 districts have the potential for Solar Energy, 2 districts for Wind Energy and 12 districts for hybrid energy generation (Combination of Solar and Wind Energy). In Kolkata, Hooghly, South 24 Parganas, wind energy as well as Hybrid Energy can be generated in the river side areas. Districts like Jalpaiguri, Cooch Behar etc. can be considered as potential hubs for Solar Energy generation.

Serial No	Districts of West Bengal	Solar Energy	Wind Energy	Hybrid Energy
1	Darjeeling	X	Yes	X
2	Jalpaiguri	Yes	Yes	Yes
3	Cooch Behar	Yes	Yes	Yes
4	Uttar Dinajpur	Yes	Yes	Yes
5	Dakshin Dinajpur	Yes	Yes	Yes
6	Malda	Yes	Yes	Yes
7	Birbhum	Yes	X	X
8	Murshidabad	Yes	X	X
9	Nadia	Yes	X	X
10	Purulia	Yes	X	X
11	Bankura	Yes	X	X
12	Hooghly	Yes	Yes	Yes
13	North 24 Parganas	Yes	Yes	Yes
14	Paschim Medinipur	Yes	X	X
15	Howrah	Yes	Yes	Yes
16	Kolkata	Yes	Yes	Yes
17	South 24 Pargana	Yes	Yes	Yes
18	Purbo Medinipur	Yes	Yes	Yes
19	Kalimpong	X	Yes	X
20	Alipurduar	Yes	Yes	Yes
21	Paschim Bardhaman	Yes	X	X
22	Jhargram	Yes	X	X
23	PurboBardhaman	Yes	X	X

Table 1 Availability of Renewable Energy districts wise

In Purbo Medinipur we can implant the wind energy in coastal areas just like Digha, Tajpur etc. Table 1 clearly shows the availability of renewable energy in the different districts of West Bengal.

The solar and wind energy statuses in West Bengal, as well as state and district-level renewable energy statuses, have been examined in this article. West Bengal's energy consumption has been increasing at a rapid pace as the state's economy has grown. With an economy which is expected to rise at 8%–9% year, accelerated urbanization, and rising living conditions for millions of households, demand is expected to skyrocket. West Bengal, like the rest of India, needs to understand the immense potential of renewable energy and ramp up efforts

to meet the 2023 deadline. These goals are attainable, and they not only have renewable resources but also open up a new field for millions of people who are unemployed or working under the table. This momentum requires to be maintained.

Solar energy, wind energy, and a mixture of the two energy sources are more efficient and simpler to use in the production of electricity. Hence, it is important to design, develop and market newer, technologically superior sources of energy. Solar and wind energies together are more cost effective in lowering power generating unit costs. During the last few years, the government has shifted its focus to implement a robust clean energy strategy and funding systems in order to give positive signals to green power generators. These renewable sources happen to be the ones. Undoubtedly, West Bengal has made a name for itself in the generation of renewable energy across India. It also has a lot of capacity for generating solar and wind energy, but there are some gaps. The Indian government has laid the groundwork for a broad-based green energy policy that is tailored to meet the country's rising energy demands and address the country's energy shortage. Thus, use of more green energy would in turn save the planet and pave the way for sustainable development.

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SOCIETY FOR
HERITAGE
ARCHAEOLOGY &
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